

SEARCH FOR THE ORIGIN OF SUBSONIC FLUTTER ON THE UHBR ECL5 FAN AT PARTIAL SPEED

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ABSTRACT

The aeroelastic stability mechanism occurring in the Ultra High Bypass Ratio fan ECL5 at 80% of nominal speed is analysed using results from 3D time-linearised Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes simulations. At the maximal pressure ratio, the second mechanical vibration mode at nodal diameter 5 induces a negative damping coefficient, meaning the fan can possibly enter into flutter. For other nodal diameters the damping coefficient is positive. The paper explores different classic aeroelastic mechanisms occurring at the second mechanical vibration mode for different nodal diameters and operating points close to the point of negative damping coefficient. At the end, analysis points out the link between this instability and the interaction between the blade and the adjacent blade tip-leakage flow.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, CFD, LRANS, Flutter, ECL5

1 INTRODUCTION

Ultra-High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) fans are the new generation of fans [1]. They are characterised by their highly three-dimensional geometries and made-up with composite materials. These particularities induce new challenge for aeroelastic instabilities prediction and new opportunity of control.

In order to study such phenomena, the community needs open configurations. For this reason, an up-to-date open test-case UHBR fan, made of 16 highly three-dimensional blades, has been designed, the ECL5 [2, 3]. The present study uses this configuration.

The analysis conducted with a linearised approach at part speed regime at the operating point of maximal pressure ratio

shows for the second vibration mode, and for the nodal diameter 5, a negative damping coefficient. This negative damping coefficient means a possible flutter phenomenon is occurring. This study explores different mechanisms to understand the origin of this negative damping: the acoustic propagation, the singularity of the numerical method, the boundary-layer separation beating and the effect of the tip-leakage flow.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Numerical methods

The numerical approach used is a 3D time-linearised Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (LRANS) approach. The stationary aerodynamic field is provided by elsA [4], a cell-centred RANS solver. The mechanical mode shape simulations are provided by finite element analysis from Ansys. Then, these two physical fields are used as inputs for the time-linearised, vertex-centred solver Turb'Lin [5], to get the flow harmonic unsteady behaviour. The coherence between the two CFD solvers has been investigated, in order to ensure there is no numerical incompatibilities between them. This methodology has been already successfully used in 2D [6], and extrapolated to 3D simulations for flutter prediction in aeronautic compressor [7]. The method being linear, and based on a steady RANS flow field, the only source of unsteadiness comes from the blades vibration.

The domain studied is a duct in which the fan is placed, without IGV or OGV. The mesh is limited to a single blade passage. It is made of 2.5M nodes. In order to avoid any reflection at inlet or outlet, the numerical domain is stretched upstream and downstream, in order to get rid of any acoustic wave

FIGURE 1: CHARACTERISTIC MAP OF THE ECL5 FAN (Nn: NOMINAL SPEED AND Π_{t-t} : TOTAL TO TOTAL PRESSURE RATIO)

return. The walls use a no-slip adiabatic condition. The inlet condition is set to the standard atmospheric conditions with a uniform turbulence level of 2% and no swirl. The outlet condition is set to constant pressure to adjust the mass flow.

Both CFD simulations use Kok $k - \omega$ turbulence model [8]. Rodrigues *et. al.* [9] validate this model using comparison to experimental data with a similar fan configuration. The turbulent kinetic energy production uses a vorticity formulation for each case. The specific turbulence dissipation at the wall ω_{wall} is approximated differently between the solvers. For the RANS solver, the value of ω is exponentially extrapolated to the wall, while for the LRANS solver, the value is put as infinite at the wall (practically : $\mathcal{O}(10^{12})$). This has been done to ensure the coherence between the two CFD solvers.

The spatial scheme used is for both simulation the Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel centred scheme [10], with a numerical dissipation to ensure its stability. The RANS simulation uses a second order coefficient $\epsilon_2 = 1/50$ and a fourth order coefficient $\epsilon_4 = 1$, while the LRANS simulations use a second order coefficient $\epsilon_2 = 1/16$ and a fourth order coefficient $\epsilon_4 = 8$. The RANS simulation uses a Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel centred scheme for the turbulent convective fluxes, while the LRANS simulations use a zeroth order upstream scheme.

2.2 Operating conditions

In this study, two operating conditions at part speed regime (80%Nn) have been analysed: OP-D, the operating point at maximal total to total pressure ratio ($\Pi_{t-t} = 1.227$), with a mass flow rate of $26 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and OP-E ($\Pi_{t-t} = 1.225$) with a larger mass flow rate at $27 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. These operating points are presented figure 1, which represents the characteristic map of the ECL5 obtained numerically via steady RANS simulations. For both operating points, the steady flow field from RANS simulation seems to be predictive enough to allow physical

analysis. The flow is subsonic and presents a boundary-layer separation on the suction side.

2.3 Notation of the modes

In the present work, a mode is the imposed mechanical vibration mode and the considered nodal diameter, and is denoted following the model of “[vibration mode]ND[Nodal diameter]”. As an example, the second vibration mode with a co-rotating nodal diameter of 4 is denoted as 2ND4.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FIGURE 2: DAMPING COEFFICIENT FOR MODE 1,2 AND 3 AT OP-D, FUNCTION OF THE NODAL DIAMETER

The numerical analysis of the aeroelastic stability is done via the aerodynamic damping coefficient ζ , defined as :

$$\zeta = \frac{W}{U} = \frac{W}{2\pi\omega^2 a_0^2 M} \quad (1)$$

with W the work of the aerodynamic forces, U the energy of deformation, ω the modal pulsation, a_0 the modal amplitude and M the modal mass. When this coefficient is positive, the aerodynamic forces have a stabilizing impact on the blade vibration, whereas when it is negative, the aerodynamic forces have a destabilising impact on the blade vibration, possibly leading to flutter.

This coefficient has been calculated for the vibration modes 1, 2 and 3, each time for various nodal diameters from -8 to 8, at OP-D. It points to a negative damping coefficient, leading to a possible entrance into flutter, for the mode 2ND5, as presented in figure 2. In comparison, at OP-D for mode 2, other ND have almost constant positive damping coefficient. In the following study, the focus is on mode 2. In order to check for the dependance of the instability to operating conditions, the damping coefficient is also calculated for mode 2 at OP-E. The fan remains notably stable at OP-E, for modes 2ND0 to 2ND6, as shown in figure 3.

In next parts, various mechanisms known to destabilise fan are discussed.

3.1 Acoustic propagation

Acoustic propagation conditions can significantly impact the aeroelastic stability. An acoustic mode is said cut-on upstream (*resp.* downstream) if it can propagate upstream (*resp.* downstream) without damping. An acoustic mode is said cut-off upstream (*resp.* downstream) if it is exponentially damped upstream (*resp.* downstream). On the one hand, Ferria *et. al.* [11] observed that a change from cut-on to cut-off produced discontinuities in the aerodynamic damping coefficient in a turbine. On the other hand, both Vahdati *et. al.* [12, 13] and Bontemps [14] evidenced that a cut-off condition downstream is linked with an increase of the local work on the blade.

FIGURE 3: DAMPING COEFFICIENT AND ACOUSTIC PROPAGATION AT OP-D AND OP-E FOR MODE 2, AS THE NODAL DIAMETER CHANGES

The acoustic propagation conditions can be determined *a priori* with the approach of Fang and Atassi [15]. However, in the present case, they have been determined *a posteriori* from LRANS solutions, with a FFT of the pressure fluctuations at

90% of the vein height along the axis. The acoustic propagation is presented in figure 3. The figure shows the damping coefficient for OP-D, for modes 2ND-8 to 2ND8, and for OP-E, for modes 2ND0 to 2ND6. The acoustic propagation condition changes between 2ND4 and 2ND5. The upstream propagation is cut-on for both, but downstream propagation is cut-on from 2ND-2 to 2ND4 and cut-off for 2ND5 and after. The energy accumulation from cut-off condition could be an explanation for the aeroelastic behaviour modification. However, it is not the relevant factor in this case for two main reasons. Firstly, acoustic conditions do not change between 2ND5 and 2ND6 at OP-D, but the damping coefficient is negative only for 2ND5. Secondly at OP-E the flow conditions are quite similar to OP-D and the acoustic conditions change in the same way than OP-D between 2ND4 and 2ND5. But the damping coefficient remains positive for all nodal diameters at OP-E without discontinuity. Another factor is thus needed to explain the negative damping coefficient.

3.2 Linear system singularity

In order to find what leads to a negative damping coefficient, the local work exchanged between the fluid and the structure along the blade is analysed. It is to notice that mode 2 presents two lobes of maximal displacement, shown figure 4. Lobe A is located close to the tip at leading edge and lobe B at mid-span, at trailing edge.

FIGURE 4: NORMALISED DISPLACEMENT AMPLITUDE FOR MODE 2

The local work is presented at OP-D for even nodal diameters on both blade sides in figure 5. Red areas are areas of positive work (stabilising), and blue areas are areas of negative work (destabilising). Local work is only significant at the tip of the blade, along all the chord, where the displacement is high (lobe A in figure 4). The displacement of lobe B doesn't seem to be linked with an area of significant work. On the suction side, the local work at the blade tip presents two sign inversions along the chord: the leading edge is a zone of negative work (area labelled "a" in figure 5) and so is the trailing edge ("c") but between the two, a zone of positive work is present ("b"). The work repartition is similar for all modes, except for 2ND6. On the pressure side, the local work at the blade tip presents also a sign inversion along the chord: from modes 2ND-2 to 2ND4, the leading edge is a zone of positive work and the trailing edge is a zone of negative work. From modes 2ND6 to

2ND-4, the opposite occurs, the leading edge is a zone of negative work and the trailing edge is a zone of positive work. So, on the pressure side, the work repartition evolves continuously from 2ND6 to 2ND4, and shows a discontinuity between 2ND4 and 2ND6.

FIGURE 5: LOCAL WORK AT OP-D FOR MODE 2, FROM ND-6 TO ND8. BLACK LINE SHOWS THE AREA WHERE THE STEADY BOUNDARY-LAYER IS SEPARATED.

As shown in figure 3, the damping coefficient is positive for 2ND4 and 2ND6, but the analysis of local work at 2ND5

reveals that these negative work areas at blade tip control the stability, as shown in Pages *et. al.* [3]. An important fact is that the magnitude of work exchanged at 2ND5 is non physical, being far too large. For this reasons no representation of local work at 2ND5 is shown here, as the assumption of small fluctuations from linearisation is not respected. The near resonance of the linearised system, that is very close to be singular, explains why the variation of the damping coefficient is so strong at 2ND5 compared to other ND, but not the fact that it is negative.

So the main questions remain, why is mode 2ND5 at OP-D prone to flutter and which is the implicated physics ? In order to understand the physics underlying these results, and due to the proximity of the two operating points, the study will now focus on OP-E and modes 2ND4 to 2ND6, because mode 2ND5 at OP-D behaviour is unpredictable numerically.

3.3 Boundary-layer separation beating

FIGURE 6: AMPLITUDE AND PHASE OF THE PRESSURE FLUCTUATIONS AT OP-E FOR MODE 2, FROM ND4 TO ND6. BLACK LINE SHOWS THE AREA WHERE THE STEADY BOUNDARY-LAYER IS SEPARATED.

Flutter has been classified as a function of the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic phenomena having hand in its occurrence. One of these kinds of flutter, detailed by Fransson [16], is the subsonic separation flutter. It occurs when the boundary-layer

FIGURE 7: UNSTEADY ENTROPY FIELD AT 90%H AT OP-E FOR MODE 2ND4

on the suction side is separated close to the leading edge due to a high incidence. This incidence is linked with a smaller rotating velocity of the blade, that occurs at 80%Nn. Under the effect of the separation, a phase-shift can occur between pressure fluctuations and the movement of the blade, that can be destabilising. In the present case, at OP-D and OP-E, the suction side boundary-layer is separated at the tip, close to the leading-edge, as shown in figures 5 and 6.

The local work being linked with fluctuations of pressure at the wall (eq. 2), both the amplitude $|\tilde{P}|$ and the phase Φ of these fluctuations are studied.

$$W = \pi \left(|\tilde{P}| \sin(\Phi) \bar{\mathbf{S}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_r \right) \quad (2)$$

with W the local work (see figure 5), \mathbf{u}_r the real part of the modal displacement (NB: the imaginary part is negligible), $|\tilde{P}|$ the pressure fluctuations amplitude and Φ the pressure fluctuations phase.

The amplitude normalised for the displacement shown figure 4 of the pressure fluctuations is presented figure 6. On the suction side, the area of maximal fluctuations is located at the tip, close to the leading edge, where the boundary layer is separated. This area coincides with the lobe A of displacement shown figure 4, and the areas “a” and “b” of local work at OP-D, shown in figure 5. The amplitude then decreases while going to the trailing edge. On the pressure side, the amplitude of the fluctuations is almost negligible, compared to the suction side, all along the blade. For both sides, the topology of the amplitude of the pressure fluctuations remains similar from 2ND4 to 2ND6 at OP-E.

The phase of the pressure fluctuations is also presented figure 6. The convention chosen here is that the fluctuations are moving in the direction of the decreasing phases. On the pressure side, the phase suggests the existence of pressure fluctuations going upstream, whose amplitude has been shown to be negligible. On the suction side, the fluctuations at the tip of the blade, where the amplitude is maximal, propagate from the leading edge to the trailing edge. The phase-shift is about 360° along the chord, inferring that the wavelength is about one chord length. By considering a mean Mach number equals to 0.5, a progressive acoustic wave would have a wavelength of about 7 times the chord length. Given the actual wavelength, the phenomenon inducing the pressure fluctuations is not acoustic, but convective. Besides, this phenomenon being insensitive to the nodal diameter from 2ND4 to 2ND6 tends to suggest that it is auto-induced by the considered blade. The main candidate is the boundary-layer separation beating.

Figure 7 presents the unsteady entropy field at 90% of vein

height for mode 2ND4 at OP-E. This mode is representative of the behaviour of the fan at OP-E for modes 2ND4 to 2ND6. The plot over a period of blade vibration shows that at some point - arbitrarily chosen at $t = 0T$ here - a burst of entropy is created at the leading edge of the blade. The burst corresponds to a beating of the boundary layer separation. This burst of entropy is then convected along the profile, to the trailing edge, over one cycle of vibration. This is coherent with the 360° phase-shift observed in figure 6. A blade-to-blade view at 90%H, given figure 8 (right-hand side for OP-E), confirms the presence of a maximum of amplitude of pressure fluctuations at the suction side (area labelled “a”), close to the leading edge. The study of the phase is also coherent with the idea of a convective phenomenon located close to the suction side, and not in the inter-blade channel or at the pressure side. It is coherent with the fact that the principal phenomenon on the suction side is the boundary-layer beating. On the pressure side, a study of the phase suggests the existence of a fluctuation going upstream, but its amplitude is negligible.

FIGURE 8: COMPARISON OF THE PRESSURE FLUCTUATIONS AMPLITUDE AND PHASE BETWEEN OP-D AND OP-E FOR MODE 2ND4 AT 90%H. THE BLADE FOR PHASE REFERENCE IS LABELLED 0.

Could a change of behaviour of the boundary-layer beating between OP-E and OP-D explain the change of stability ? To find it, the pressure fluctuations amplitude and phase are compared between OP-D and OP-E for mode 2ND4 at 90%H, as presented figure 8. First, the boundary-layer beating is also present at OP-D (area “a”). The amplitude and phase of the pressure fluctuations are quite similar on the suction side of the blades between OP-D and OP-E. However, for OP-D, pressure fluctuations are present over all the width of the interblade channel (area “b”). Concerning the phase of the fluctuations, it is different between the two operating points inside the channel and close to the pressure side. For OP-D, the phenomenon is not a negligible fluctuation going upstream, but a non-negligible fluctuation convected downstream. Given the position of this convected phenomenon, it seems to be linked with the tip-leakage flow.

The boundary-layer beating being present for both OP-D and OP-E with no distinctive difference except amplitude, it is not enough to explain the switch from stable at OP-E to unstable at OP-D. Next, the study focuses on the second phenomenon present at OP-D, linked with the tip-leakage flow.

3.4 Tip-leakage flow

In order to focus the study of the tip-leakage flow and its effects over the stability for mode 2ND4 at OP-D, figure 9 presents the unsteady entropy field at 98% of vein height. The figure is plotted over one period of blade vibration. At some point - arbitrarily chosen at $t = 0T$ here - a burst of entropy is created at the leading edge of the blade on the suction side. This burst is labelled “a₁”, and corresponds to the boundary-layer beating, previously highlighted figure 8 left at 90%H. The burst is then convected to the trailing edge, in the same way as it is at OP-E, thus the area labelled “a₀” corresponds to the boundary-layer beating from the previous vibration cycle. A second phenomenon is also visible. A burst of entropy appears at the leading edge, close to the suction side (area “b₁”) at $t = 0T$. This local area of significant entropy is then convected inside the channel, by the tip-leakage flow. It takes about one cycle of vibration of the blade to reach the adjacent blade, thus the area labelled “b₀” corresponds to the same phenomenon from the previous vibration cycle.

The comparison between OP-D and OP-E amplitude and phase of the pressure fluctuations at 98% of vein height is presented in figure 10. Close to the suction side, the amplitude and phase of the pressure fluctuations are similar between OP-D and OP-E. A convective phenomenon, linked with the boundary-layer beating, is visible (area “a”). Inside the channel and close to the pressure side, the fluctuations are quite different, both in amplitude and phase, between the two operating points. For OP-D, the burst of entropy previously seen in figure 9 is linked with a significant amplitude of fluctuations (area “b”). Conversely, for OP-E, at area “b”, the fluctuations amplitude remains low. At OP-D, the iso-phase lines cover all the channel width, from suction side to pressure side. The propagation goes in the same direction as the flow, inferring a dominance of the convective phenomenon linked with the tip-leakage flow. At OP-E, the phase is similar to what was seen at 90%H, figure 8.

FIGURE 9: UNSTEADY ENTROPY FIELD AT 98%H AT OP-D FOR MODE 2ND4

FIGURE 10: COMPARISON OF THE PRESSURE FLUCTUATIONS AMPLITUDE AND PHASE BETWEEN OP-D AND OP-E FOR MODE 2ND4 AT 98%H. THE BLADE FOR PHASE REFERENCE IS LABELLED 0.

The next step is to understand the phenomenal causality that explains how the tip-leakage flow has a dominant destabilising effect only at 2ND5.

3.5 Tip-leakage flow characteristic time

One possible explanation of the destabilising effect of the tip-leakage flow for mode 2ND5 at OP-D can be found in Moller *et. al.* [17]: unstable configurations can appear when there is a concordance between the fluctuation propagation velocity and the circumferential velocity of the flow. In the present study, an analogous approach is chosen, based on characteristic times. The destabilising effect of the tip-leakage flow can be linked with the time that it takes for the burst of entropy fluctuations to be transported through the channel, and to impact the adjacent blade. Given that the fluctuations of entropy are only convected, the convection time t_{cv} is estimated by doing the ratio between the distance travelled by “b₁” in figure 9 and the velocity of the steady flow field. Concerning the time associated with the inter-blade phasing angle t_{ND} , it is defined as follows :

$$t_{ND} = \frac{\sigma_{ND}}{2\pi} \frac{1}{f} \quad (3)$$

with σ_{ND} the inter-blade phase-shift and f the modal frequency. Practically speaking, when considering two blades, one of reference and one adjacent, it is the time needed for the adjacent blade to reach the same state of its vibration cycle as the reference one is in at time $t = 0T$.

In order to test this hypothesis, two solutions are available. Either modifying the convective time or modifying the inter-blade phasing angle time. The LRANS method allows to modify both, but the modification of the convective time amounts to modify the mean flow velocity, thus the operating point. The former solution, the modification of the inter-blade phasing angle time, is more convenient in that case, given that it only needs to modify the modal frequency value. This solution is chosen.

The change is made such as the ratio t_{cv}/t_{ND} covers the range [0.95, 1.15] for 2ND4, 2ND5 and 2ND6 at OP-D. This range corresponds to the ratios predicted by the mechanical solver for 2ND4 to 2ND6. The results are presented in figure 11. For each curve, the circled point represents the value of t_{ND} given by the mechanical solver. It shows that for the three modes, the damping coefficient switches to negative close to and after $t_{cv}/t_{ND} \approx 1.06$. For 2ND4 and 2ND6, the vibration frequencies given by the mechanical solver are far from the switch value. For 2ND5, it is close to the switch value. This study gives two pieces of information. Firstly, when the ratio $t_{cv}/t_{ND} \approx 1.06$, the work exchange of the blade is amplified. It takes the burst of entropy fluctuations just the right time to travel through the inter-blade channel and to have a destabilising interaction with the adjacent blade. Secondly, it means that the burst is received by the adjacent blade almost at the same time the adjacent blade emits its own burst. The link between this fact and the destabilising effect of the interaction has not yet been explained.

FIGURE 11: DAMPING COEFFICIENT ζ OF THE AEROELASTIC RESPONSE FUNCTION OF THE RATIO BETWEEN THE CONVECTION TIME t_{cv} AND THE TIME RELATED TO THE INTER-BLADE PHASING ANGLE t_{ND} FOR MODE 2, FOR ND4, ND5 AND ND6, AT OP-D. THE CIRCLED POINTS REPRESENT THE VALUES OF t_{ND} GIVEN BY THE MECHANICAL SOLVER.

The fact that for the three modes, the negative value appears for the same ratio t_{cv}/t_{ND} , reinforces the idea that the negative damping coefficient at 2ND5 at OP-D is not due to a numerical effect, linked with the proximity of the linear system singularity. It proves that the instability observed at 2ND5 at OP-D is due to the interaction between the reference blade vibration, tip-leakage flow fluctuations and the adjacent blade vibration.

4 CONCLUSION

The study with a linearised RANS approach of the flow aeroelastic mechanisms occurring at part speed, at the point of maximal pressure ratio, shows a negative damping coefficient, which can lead to an entry into flutter, for the blade vibration mode 2 at nodal diameter 5.

This phenomenon has not been found linked with the change of acoustic conditions, nor boundary-layer separation beating. It seems to be directly linked with a convective mechanism. The convection time of the tip-leakage flow fluctuations through the blade passage, at this nodal diameter, is close to the time corresponding to the inter-blade phase angle, leading to a resonance which could induce flutter.

A complementary study, using non-linear simulations, has also been realised on the ECL5 open test-case, by Fiquet *et. al.* [18].

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REFERENCES

- [1] Epstein A. H. “Aer propulsion for Commercial Aviation in the Twenty-First Century and Research Directions Needed”. In: *AIAA Journal* 52 (5 2014), pp. 901–911. ISSN: 0001-1452, 1533-385X. DOI: : 10 . 2514/1 . J052713.

- [2] Christoph Brandstetter, Valdo Pagès, Pierre Duquesne, Xavier Ottavy, and Pascal Ferrand. “UHBR OPEN TEST-CASE FAN ECL5/CATANA PART 1: GEOMETRY AND AERODYNAMIC PERFORMANCE.” In: *14th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics*. Gdansk, Poland, Apr. 2021.
- [3] Valdo Pagès, Pierre Duquesne, Stéphane Aubert, Laurent Blanc, and Pascal Ferrand. “UHBR OPEN TEST-CASE FAN ECL5/CATANA, PART 2: MECHANICAL AND AEROELASTIC STABILITY ANALYSIS.” In: *14th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics*. Gdansk, Poland, Apr. 2021.
- [4] Cambier, Laurent, Heib, Sébastien, and Plot, Sylvie. “The Onera elsA CFD software: input from research and feedback from industry”. In: *Mechanics & Industry* 14.3 (2013), pp. 159–174.
- [5] M. Philit, P. Ferrand, S. Labit, J.-C. Chassaing, S. Aubert, and T. Fransson. “Derivated Turbulence Model to Predict Harmonic Loads in Transonic Separated Flows over a Bump”. In: *28th International Congress of the Aeronautical Sciences, ICAS*. Brisbane, Australia, 2012. ISBN: 978-0-9565333-1-9.
- [6] P. Duquesne, B. Mahieux, S. Aubert, and P. Ferrand. “Sensitivity of the aerodynamics damping coefficient prediction to the turbulence modelling conjugated with the vibration mode shape”. In: *Proceedings of 13th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics ETC13*. Lausanne, Switzerland, 2019.
- [7] Pierre Duquesne, Bruno Mahieux, Stéphane Aubert, and Pascal Ferrand. “3D effects on flutter prediction in aeronautic compressor”. In: *24ème Congrès Français de Mécanique*. Brest, France: Association Française de Mécanique, Aug. 2019.
- [8] Johan C. Kok. “Resolving the Dependence on Freestream Values for the k-w Turbulence Model”. In: *AIAA Journal* 38.7 (2000), pp. 1292–1295. DOI: 10.2514/2.1101.
- [9] M. Rodrigues, L. Soulat, B. Paoletti, X. Ottavy, and C. Brandstetter. “Aerodynamic investigation of a composite low-speed fan for UHBR application”. In: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2020 & Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*. London, UK: ASME, 2020.
- [10] A. Jameson, Wolfgang Schmidt, and Eli Turkel. “Numerical solution of the Euler equations by finite volume methods using Runge Kutta time stepping schemes”. In: *14th Fluid and Plasma Dynamics Conference*. Palo Alto, CA, U.S.A.: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, June 1981.
- [11] Hakim Ferria, Pascal Ferrand, François Pacull, and Stéphane Aubert. “Numerical investigation of flutter stability in subsonic space turbine blisk with emphasis on cut-on/cut-off modes and interblade phase angles”. In: *Journal of Thermal Science* 21.6 (Dec. 2012), pp. 492–499. ISSN: 1003-2169, 1993-033X.
- [12] Mehdi Vahdati, Nigel Smith, and Fanzhou Zhao. “Influence of Intake on Fan Blade Flutter”. In: *Journal of Turbomachinery* 137.8 (Aug. 2015), p. 081002.
- [13] Mehdi Vahdati and Nick Cumpsty. “Aeroelastic Instability in Transonic Fans”. In: *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 138.2 (Sept. 2015), p. 022604.
- [14] Thomas Bontemps. “Flottement fan et couplage acoustique : analyse et modélisation”. PhD thesis. ECL, 2021.
- [15] Jisheng Fang and Hafiz M. Atassi. “Compressible Flows with Vortical Disturbances Around a Cascade of Loaded Airfoils”. In: *Unsteady Aerodynamics, Aeroacoustics, and Aeroelasticity of Turbomachines and Propellers*. Ed. by H. M. Atassi. New York, NY: Springer New York, 1993, pp. 149–176.
- [16] Torsten H Fransson. *Aeroelasticity In Axial-Flow Turbomachines*. von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics, 1999.
- [17] Daniel Moller, Maximilian Jüngst, Felix Holzinger, Christoph Brandstetter, Heinz-Peter Schiffer, and Sebastian Leichtfus. “Numerical Investigation of Tip Clearance Flow Induced Flutter in an Axial Research Compressor”. In: *Volume 7B: Structures and Dynamics*. Seoul, South Korea: ASME, June 2016, V07BT34A010.
- [18] A.-L. Fiquet, X Ottavy, and C. Brandstetter. “UHBR open-test case fan ECL5/CATANA: non-linear analysis of non-synchronous blade vibration at part-speed conditions”. In: *16th International Symposium on Unsteady Aerodynamics Aeroacoustics and Aeroelasticity of Turbomachines*. Toledo, Spain: ISUAAAT16, Sept. 2022.